

Synthesis of 1-(Arylideneaminoethyl)-2-phenyl-4-(3',5'-dibromo-2'-hydroxybenzylidene)imidazolin-5-ones

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1-(Arylideneaminoethyl)-2-phenyl-4-(3',5'-dibromo-2'-hydroxybenzylidene)imidazolin-5-ones were synthesised by the condensation of 2-phenyl-4-(3',5'-dibromo-2'-hydroxybenzylidene)oxazolin-5-one and ethylenediamine in pyridine, followed by reaction with the appropriate aldehyde in ethanol containing a few drops of glacial acetic acid. The compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity

THE benzylidene imidazolinone chemistry with its diverse biological properties like central nervous system depressant¹, anticonvulsant², and monoamineoxidase inhibitor³ has received importance in recent years. The benzylideneimidazolinones has also been reported to possess the analgesic and muscle relaxant properties⁴. The structural modification with pharmacologically active grouping has shown excellent results in pharmacology. With a view to extend the scope and validity of these observations, we report herein the synthesis of the title benzylideneimidazolinone derivatives to study their antibacterial efficacy. The choice of imidazolone derivatives arose because their number of analogues have been shown to exhibit biological activities including antibacterial properties. Compounds were synthesised according to the sequence of reactions outlined in Scheme 1.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Backmann IR 20 spectrophotometer. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, counter synthesis, m.m.p. and ir spectra. The ir spectra of the compounds showing characteristic bands at 1 680 (C=O of imidazoline), 1 700 1 690 (C=O of CONH), 1 645 (C=N of imidazolone), 1 600-1 610 (C=C str.) and 3 00-2 990 (CH₂ str.) supported the validity of the compounds.

2-Phenyl-4-(3',5'-dibromo-2'-hydroxybenzylidene)oxazolin-5-one: The reported^{5,6} procedure was used to synthesise the required oxazolin-5-one.

1-(Aminoethyl)-2-phenyl-4-(3',5'-dibromo-2'-hydroxybenzylidene)imidazolin-5-one: A mixture of 2-phenyl-4-(3',5'-dibromo-2'-hydroxybenzylidene)oxazolin-5-one (0.5 mol) and ethylenediamine (0.5 mol)

in pyridine (50 ml) was heated under reflux for 8 h. The solvent was then distilled off under reduced

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE IMIDAZOLES

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen % : Found/(Calcd.)
1.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂	116	54	7.19 (7.38)
2.	3-OH.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂	152	55	7.21 (7.38)
3.	2-OH-5-Br.C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ Br ₃ N ₃ O ₂	129	57	6.29 (6.48)
4.	3,5(Br) ₂ -2-OH.C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ Br ₄ N ₃ O ₂	106	54	5.58 (5.77)
5.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₄	159	62	6.89 (7.01)
6.	5-Br-4-OH-3-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ Br ₃ N ₃ O ₄	140	58	6.00 (6.19)
7.	4-OH-5-I-3-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ BrIN ₃ O ₄	122	57	5.60 (5.79)
8.	2-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂	148	55	7.01 (7.20)
9.	3,4(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₄	111	62	6.66 (6.85)
10.	5-Br-3,4(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ Br ₃ N ₃ O ₄	104	58	5.88 (6.06)
11.	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₆	123	58	6.35 (6.53)
12.	3,4-(OCH ₂ O).C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₄	131	54	6.90 (7.04)
13.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ Br ₂ ClN ₃ O ₂	133	54	7.00 (7.14)
14.	3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₄	146	55	9.10 (9.36)
15.	2-OH-1-naphthyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂	110	60	6.59 (6.78)

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY DATA OF THE IMIDAZOLES

Sl. no.	R	Antibacterial activity of type I	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	+	-
2.	3-OH.C ₆ H ₄	-	-
3.	2-OH-5-Br.C ₆ H ₃	+	-
4.	2-OH-3,5(Br) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	+	+
5.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	+	-
6.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -5-Br.C ₆ H ₃	+	-
7.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -5-I.C ₆ H ₃	+	+
8.	2-OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	-	+
9.	3,4(OCH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	+	+
10.	3,4,5(OCH ₃) ₃ -5-Br.C ₆ H ₃	+	+
11.	3,4,5(OCH ₃) ₃ .C ₆ H ₃	+	-
12.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	-	-
13.	3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	+	-
14.	3,4(OCH ₂ O).C ₆ H ₃	-	-
15.	2-OH-1-naphthyl	+	+

(+) = Inhibition zone occurs. (-) = No inhibition zone occurs.

pressure. The crude product was diluted with acidified water and allowed to stand for 4 h at room temperature. The solid were filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

1-(Arylideneaminoethyl)-2-phenyl-4-(3',5'-dibromo-2'-hydroxybenzylidene)imidazolin-5-ones: A mixture of 1-(aminoethyl)-2-phenyl-4-(3',5'-dibromo-2'-

hydroxybenzylidene)imidazolin-5 one (0.01 mol), appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mol) and ethanol (50 ml) containing a few drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. Ethanol was then distilled off and the crude product was washed with water, filtered, then washed with petroleum ether and solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Pharmacological screening: 1-(Arylideneaminoethyl)-2-phenyl-4-(3',5'-dibromo-2'-hydroxybenzylidene)imidazolin-5-ones were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

Results and Discussion

Antibacterial assay: Out of 15 compounds, 11 compounds were found to be active against gram +ve bacteria, i.e. *S. aureus* and 6 compounds active against gram -ve bacteria, i.e. *E. coli*; and 5 compounds active against both the species. Compounds having 3,5-dibromo-2-hydroxy, 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-5-iodo, 3,4-dimethoxy, 5-bromo-3,4-dimethoxy and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl substitutions were active against both the species. The data are recorded in Table 2.

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